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Refusal as Resistance: Food and the Distorted Self in Han Kang's

The Vegetarian

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Abstract:

In most cultures, food transcends its role as a basic requirement and acts as a symbolic language threaded through identity, memory, and cognitive experience. Han Kang's novel *The Vegetarian* portrays food as a cultural marker of conventionality, femininity, and social conditioning, where it becomes a medium through which society imposes power and dominance. This paper aims to explore the convergences of food, psyche, and gender issues in Korean culture as represented in Kang's text. It also examines how these factors perpetuate patriarchal control, while Yeong-hye's subversive choices challenge these norms. Drawing on psychoanalytic theory, this article mainly elevates food as a symbol of gendered regulation as well as Yeong-hye's resistance to the structured roles constructed by society. It also reveals how the body and its relationship to food articulate trauma and repression.

Keywords: *The Vegetarian*, food and psyche, abjection, and repression.

Introduction:

Han Kang's magnum opus, *The Vegetarian*, written originally in Korean and translated into English by Deborah Smith, was first published in 2007. It is set in Seoul and revolves around the protagonist Yeong-hye, who experiences a horrifying dream that leads to psychological tensions and conflicts in her life. It unravels her life, and she decides to become a vegetarian after that dream sets off a series of challenges, triggering emotional turmoil. The novel consists of three parts: *The Vegetarian*, *Mongolian Mark*, and *Flaming Trees*. The first section unfolds through a first-person narrative by Mr. Cheong, Yeong-hye's husband. Being a conventional man, upholding normative values, he expects his wife to be obedient and spend her life taking care of him and their household. She adheres to a conventional life, striving to fulfil social obligations, for which she is considered a devoted wife. He even characterises her as absolutely unremarkable in every way because she performs her domestic responsibilities with conformity to traditional gender roles. He asserts, "There's nothing wrong with keeping quiet; after all hadn't women traditionally been expected to be demure and restrained?" (Kang 21), which depicts her as a woman of few words, lacking agency, whose silence is never a concern to her husband. She embodies a dutiful wife, abiding by his orders until she had that dream. However, when she starts defying all those social expectations, everything changes, and she is depicted as an altered self, transgressing social conventions. She refuses to eat meat because she conceives it as a symbol of violence, and her father, knowing this, slaps her for not conforming to the patriarchal ideals of her family. In response, she cuts her wrist to escape from the control imposed over her body. This act marks the outset of her metamorphosis. Also, it triggers her repressed childhood trauma and haunting memory of being forced to eat the meat of her pet dog, killed by her authoritarian father.

The second section of the novel presents the perspective of her brother-in-law. He appears as the artist husband of Yeong-hye's elder sister, In-hye. He is obsessed with Yeong-

hye's Mongolian mark on her buttocks, which looks like a flower petal, so he convinces her to pose nude for his sketches. In-hye's husband tries to break the boundaries by having sex with Yeong-hye with a painted body. She accepts his request because she wishes to do whatever she desires with her body without anyone's orders. When he sees her naked, he realises something about her body, perceiving it as "the body of a beautiful young woman, conventionally an object of desire, and yet it was a body from which all desire had been eliminated" (Kang 85), which shows her transformation.

The final section portrays Yeong-hye's relationship with her sister In-hye, depicting the harsh truths of their intertwined fates. It is the most pivotal part of the novel, as it shows her desire for a plant-like life to stay away from human brutality as she rebels against violence. Yeong hye's decision to reclaim her body as far as her sexual desires are concerned serves to reiterate her agency. She refuses to consume anything except water and expresses her wish to become a tree, as it does not hurt anyone or anything to survive. These thoughts drive her into anorexia nervosa, as claimed by the doctors, but for her, it was a moment of revelation through which she breaks the symbolic order. She shows her rebellion of the 'self' to conform to any societal constraints and the innocent wish to lead a virtuous life, but, in the end, she understands that it is impossible to reclaim one's innocence because humanity is inherently detrimental.

On the other hand, In-hye feels isolated because no one understands her. At the end of the text, she alone was there for Yeong-hye, and she desires to connect with her sister, driving her to share the same madness that her sister undergoes. Having followed the societal norms of a conventional wife she realizes at the end that she has never truly lived her life. Exploration of Yeong-hye and In-hye's characters provides shared psychological experiences, in which both descend into breakdown. Although she conformed to cultural norms, her life remained meaningless, and her psychological disintegration is depicted through isolation, whereas Yeong-hye rebels directly but fails, like her sister. Her internalized suffering does not arise from

a rejection of food, like Yeong-hye's, but from meaninglessness. In this way, the sisters' lives and struggles unfold within a single framework, where one shows visible revolt and the other silent endurance. Both endure pain within patriarchal structures, and their paths illuminate different projections of psychic collapse. Eventually, In-hye begins to understand her sister's thoughts, and at one point she even tells herself that it's "your body; you can treat it however you please. The only area where you're free to do just as you like. And even that doesn't turn out how you wanted" (Kang 177). Her change in perspective fails to serve any purpose as she continues to be oppressed by societal pressures.

Culinary Constraints and the Female Psyche:

The text significantly connects food to the psyche, so drawing from the works of Julia Kristeva and psychoanalytic theory, this paper examines how Yeong-hye's choices demonstrate a fragmented psyche navigating through repressed trauma and haunting memories. By refusing to eat, Yeong-hye initiates her first rebellion against norms through food. Her decision to lead a life according to her wish enrages her husband, and his attitude towards her exposes how women's food choices demand submission to patriarchal expectations. As Michael J. Pettid elucidates, "The bonds between food and the physical and mental cultures of Korea are inseparable. There is simply no division between Korea, Koreans, and the cuisine of Korea" (10), highlighting how culinary practice reflects Confucian-influenced Korean identity. This identity firmly ties to Yeong-hye's refusal to eat, which aligns with her rejection of collective identity. Yeong-hye subverts gendered oppression by rejecting meat, which is associated with customary Korean identity. Her abstention from sex also frustrates her husband, and when he forces her to get physically involved with him, he projects the view of women as just materials for male satisfaction. Her comment that his body smells like meat and her further refusal to have sex with him results in a marital crisis. Her psyche, haunted by horrific memories and dreams, makes her break the image of women projected only as materials. He cares only for

her body and views it as a site of consumption. Her vegetarianism is found to be the root cause of change in her behaviour and hence refusal to satisfy his bodily needs. He says, “Well then, that means you need to eat some meat. That’s why you don’t have any energy any more, right?” (Kang 16-17), demonstrating how food functions as a means of dominance and suppression of the female body. His outlook on her body as merely a commodity reflects his inner perspective of considering women only as objects used to gratify sexual hunger, which again relates sex to food. So here, both provide a platform where male desire is favoured and women are objectified. However, her silence and refusal to do all these dismantle commodification.

In Korean culture, meat is not only a part of the food routine but also a tool of masculine hegemony. Korean Orthodox families inculcate meat cultures deeply. In an article discussing food and Korean national identity, Cho Hong Sik quoted Monica L. Smith: “[T]he act of consuming food may represent the basic locus of identity, conformity and resistance” (210), which testifies to how food is a national symbol connecting to concepts like tradition and culture constructed by the society. Yeong-hye belongs to one such family, so when she confesses that she has turned vegetarian, her family altogether disowns her, leaving her isolated for disrupting conformity to tradition. Pettid explains that “the kitchen was a woman’s space can be further seen in that the deity of the kitchen was female” (144), explicating how the kitchen reflects the gender-based segregation of space in traditional Korean society. By glorifying women through association with a goddess, this cultural framework normalises women’s sufferings within domestic roles. Abstention from food in Yeong-hye’s life acts as a primary agent in shaping her fragmented psyche. Nevertheless, according to her family members, conforming to traditional food habits shapes one’s behavioural traits related to physical and mental health. So, her rejection of all those conformed regulations creates psychological tensions, revealing how society often overlooks women’s psychic struggle. When she resists to enter the kitchen, she is labeled as irrational and insane . Her family thus

fails to comprehend her desire to transform. In the first section of the novel, Yeong-hye's husband invites his boss and the boss's wife over for dinner, and there they all discuss how vegetarianism goes against human nature. Everyone who knows that she has become a vegetarian is astonished by her choice and sympathizes with Mr. Cheong for having a disrespectful wife. They all believe that a wife should readily accept the conventional practices of family life. They assert meat-eating as a "fundamental human instinct, which means vegetarianism goes against human nature, right? It just isn't natural" (Kang 23), which brings to light how society labels individuals who abstain from meat as rigid and inflexible. According to them, reasons for abstaining from meat should be either religion-based or due to medical conditions. The dominant order considers any other reasons abnormal and marginalises those who do not fit into the socially constructed standards. So, her abstention creates chaos and disorder within her family. Thus, her refusal to consume food can be interpreted as a narrative of resistance against national ideology and the exaltation of traditional cuisine, revealing the violent psychic and gendered consequences of such collective cultural and political constructions encompassing various forms of structures.

This article positions *The Vegetarian* within psychoanalytic discourse and primarily explores Julia Kristeva's theory of abjection. Her theory of abjection offers a critical framework to evaluate Yeong-hye's disgust towards certain food items, and in the end, she completely discards food. For Kristeva, abjection exhibits how humans act toward elements that threaten their boundaries or create a distinction between the subject and the object. In her book, *Powers of Horror: An Essay on Abjection*, she explains, "Food becomes abject only if it is a border between two distinct entities or territories. A boundary between nature and culture, between the human and the non-human" (5). She also states, "Food loathing is perhaps the most elementary and most archaic form of abjection" (2). In this sense, for Yeon-hye, meat becomes abject because it reminds her of violence and objectification. The novel overflows with dreams

of blood and raw flesh, which display the return of the repressed, a concept that echoes the work of Freud. Through those repressed memories and horrifying dreams, Yeong-hye confronts her traumas, projecting the disintegration of her self. She believes she can photosynthesise and so declares she no longer needs food, only sunlight. She refuses subjugation through food and sexuality, seeking to transform from human to tree, thereby unveiling a symbolic withdrawal from society's demands. Her refusal to live according to others represents a form of existential rebellion confronting the absurdity of human existence. She shows that existence is meaningless, with culture and hegemony breaking the essence of an authentic. Through a series of dreams, she unfolds her breakdown, exploring the suppression of her unconscious and desires. Though she has a gruesome dream, it proves to be an awakening call to her, and without that dream, she could not have wrestled with the silent subjugation, especially with food and its correlation to identity. She outlines the dream distinctly as follows:

Dark woods. No people. The sharp-pointed leaves on the trees, my torn feet. This place, almost remembered, but I'm lost now. Frightened. Cold. Across the frozen ravine, a red barn-like building. Straw matting flapping limp across the door. Roll it up and I'm inside, it's inside. Long bamboo sticks strung with great blood-red gashes of meat, blood still dripping down. Try to push past but the meat, there's no end to the meat, and no exit. Blood in my mouth, blood-soaked clothes sucked onto my skin. (Kang 12)

Yeong-hye's recurring dreams of blood and slaughter are highly significant and resonate with Freud's view that our "dreams always unite themselves with those ideas which have shortly before been in our consciousness" (5). In her case, the dream mirrors her past trauma, fusing with the waking state. Her experience becomes a psychic reflection through which suppressed childhood memories re-emerge. She disrupts the cultural practices that define her as a woman. Yeong-hye's dream is unsettling, and it cannot be dismissed as a silly dream because it has more profound implications connecting past and present. Her dreams pave

the way to self-revelation and a change of thought relating remembrance to resistance and subversion to transformation. That is why immediately after awakening from the dream, she instinctively moves to the kitchen and discards every trace of meat into the trash without realising the consequences she is going to face. Her withdrawal from language signifies the rejection of the Symbolic order, as suggested by Lacan. This order shapes individual existence and identity, so by refusing to speak and abstaining from food, Yeong-hye defies the structures that situate her within patriarchal society. By consuming silence, she depicts her collapse into the domain of the Real, reverberating Jacques Lacan's concept, where her withdrawal into vegetarianism and her transformation toward a plant-like existence exhibit a shift toward the Real. However, from a psychoanalytic perspective, Yeong-hye's struggles can be analysed as an attempt to bring a shift in her life through the terminal act of cleansing the self from the horrible experiences she underwent in her past. Her unconscious explodes when repression fails, destabilising not only her individual self but also the entire social circle that depends on her, and her refusal of meat is firmly rooted in trauma from memories of childhood. Abstaining from food can be explored through the way of remembering or resisting, so Yeong-hye's decision to reject meals can be interpreted as the retrieval of her childhood memories and past traumas resurfacing again, where food became a vessel for her to resist patriarchal norms. Through the process of abjection, she rejects whatever disturbs her identity. As the novel progresses, she becomes almost vegetal by rejecting food, which shows her subversion of conventional standards that disrupts her selfhood.

Cho Hong Sik, in his article "Food and Nationalism: Kimchi and Korean National Identity," explores how people perceive kimchi as a symbol of cultural pride and unity in Korea (210). In contrast, Yeong-hye's rejection of food demonstrates a defiance of nationalist discourse rather than just personal trauma, and her abjection challenges the notion that the female body must represent a nation. If kimchi, as Cho suggests, is the culinary emblem of

Korean identity, then Yeong-hye's refusal to eat becomes a negation of that emblem. In this way, *The Vegetarian* disrupts nationalism that beautifies the body as a bearer of culture and instead proclaims the agency of the self. Her rebellion is also against the deeply embedded Confucian norms that govern South Korean society. Confucianism prescribes obedience and strict gender roles, forcing women to be silent in society. A cultivated moral code is imposed on her, wherein her refusal serves as a metaphorical rejection of subjugation through cultural means. Her transformation from a submissive wife to a plant-like figure signifies a rebellious detachment from the worldview that seeks to regulate the female body through family, food, and duty. Thus, Yeong-hye's trauma becomes a domain where cultural and psychological resistances intersect. By disturbing the gaps and silences within custom, she deconstructs the historically entrenched structures of order that shape Korean society itself.

Through the story of Yeong-hye, the novel delves deeply into the psychological elements of food refusal and trauma. It provides insights into how Yeong-hye's relationship with food reveals deeper psychological resistances. Yeong-hye's refusal to obey the regulations of culturally imposed roles provokes scorn from her father, who berates her and says, "Acting like this at your age, what on earth must Mr. Cheong think?" (Kang 29). It shows how her family never cared for her, and they only thought about her husband. They never want her to rebel against the system, but her inclination to denounce earthly life is stronger, and so she starts resisting with food, marking the primary domain of obstinacy against prescribed norms. Her vegetal transformation represents an attempt to escape a life filled with despair and unseen suffering. When she throws away the meat, Mr. Cheong calls her insane, and he states, "Stop eating meat, and the world will devour you whole" (Kang 48), which depicts how food is symbolic of social structures constructing feminine roles. Thus, food becomes the very language through which Yeong-hye processes trauma and asserts a rebellion of the self. Her

refusal to eat, to speak, or to function within human norms reveals the in-depth pain of her psychic wounds and her desperate need for autonomy.

Conclusion:

The Vegetarian offers a discourse that critiques patriarchal norms through the symbolic language of food, gender, and the psyche. Throughout the text, Yeong-hye projects a form of resistance against dominant systems that objectify the female self by refraining from meat, sexual intimacy, and even human existence itself. She descends into silence, displaying a psychic protest rooted in repression, memory, and trauma. Her refusal to consume food, which is a representation of pride and identity, becomes a silent revolt against the forces of cultural conditioning. So, *The Vegetarian* delves not into a celebration of typical Korean cuisine; rather, it presents a poignant exposition of how systems of dominance and control immerse food and identity. In this way, Yeong-hye's self-imposed starvation becomes an act of feminist disobedience, and by engaging psychoanalytic frameworks, the novel emphasises how food refusal becomes an embodiment of more profound psychic rupture. Ultimately, Yeong-hye's urge for transformation reveals how the female body becomes an arena for the reclamation of agency, as food transcends its corporeality to become a language of defiance and to mirror the distorted self.

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